

Hello and welcome to the first LNL Community Newsletter

This new monthly newsletter will provide information about resources and activities to help make your job as LNL easier. We will showcase LNL activities and achievements, give you opportunities to get involved in open research activities and hopefully provide some inspiration and food for thought.

The newsletter is a great place to share your LNL activities and plans. It's your newsletter. What content would you like to see? Would you like to be a guest editor? Let us know, get in touch contact@ukrn.org

The newsletter will arrive by email, it will also be stored on the UKRN website as a lasting resource for your reference and as a means to recognise and raise the profile of LNLs and the work that you do.

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Please read on...and let us know what you think.

New guide to open science

Lots of people claim to have a book inside them, LNL Charlotte Pennington has made hers a reality. Earlier this year she published *A Student's Guide to Open Science: using the Replication Crisis to Reform Psychology*.

Charlotte mentioned her book during the recent LNL Retreat and so the central UKRN team decided to buy a copy. The book is a great introduction to open science, Charlotte writes in a clear and accessible way. It's like sitting down for a cup of tea and a chat with a friend. Charlotte begins by explaining how the replication crisis affected her early career. Providing this personal context draws you into the book as you learn more about the events that caused the replication crisis in psychology and the range of open science practices that can improve replication and reproducibility across scientific disciplines.

There are top tips, quotes and case studies alongside activities for you to try as well as links to lots of resources and organisations. It's very much a book of opportunities and is already being called the new 'Open Science Bible'.

Recommended reading for students and supervisors alike.

[Charlotte's book](#)

UKRN resources for you

There are lots of resources on the UKRN website that can help your network members learn more about open research. You can also share these resources to help increase awareness and make the case for open research more widely

in your institution.

Animation

This one is a 3 minute animation about data sharing - it covers a lot of ground in its 3 minutes - and can help you make a compelling case for data sharing.

[Data sharing animation](#)

Primers

There are primers aimed at both researchers and professional services staff. These contain everything you need to know about an open research topic using a straight forward 'what', 'why' and 'how' approach.

For example - a Checklist for an Open Research Action Plan

[Checklist primer](#)

For example - How to run an Open Research Award

[Award primer](#)

ReproducibiliTea Journal Club

Many of you already know about [ReproducibiliTea](#) and may have the teapot to prove it. For those who don't, ReproducibiliTea is a journal club started in 2018 by Sophia Crüwell, Amy Orben, and Sam Parsons at the University of Oxford, which now operates worldwide. Amy explains their rationale [here](#)

Researchers can set up journal clubs at their own institution, or join online clubs anywhere in the world. There are 33 UK-based clubs, some of them established or run by LNLs. For LNLs wanting to start a club, contacting existing clubs is a good place to ask for advice.

A ReproducibiliTea club can also be a way to link your local network members with fellow open research advocates and enthusiasts at your institution and to increase your own professional connections. A useful summary video can be found [here](#)

[ReproducibiliTea video](#)

OpenResearch Calendar

Want to know what's going on elsewhere in the world of open research?

Look no further.

The OpenResearch Calendar collates lots of events, happenings and opportunities in one place. There may be events of interest to your local network members. It's also a great way for you to share your LNL activities with the rest of the world!

[OpenResearch calendar](#)

Photo credit: Maike und Björn Bröskamp - Pixabay

Upcoming UKRN webinar - antibodies

[Antibodies and Research Reproducibility](#)

21st September 2023 1:00 - 3:00 pm

Antibodies are known to be an important driver of irreproducibility in research.

Like many other reproducibility problems in research an effective solution likely involves changes to the research environment and culture. The Only Good Antibodies community was set up to try to address this problem. It is a diverse cross disciplinary collaboration of individuals and partner organisations with interests in biomedical research, behavioural science, meta science, data science and research assessment. This seminar will introduce the problem, primarily with a focus on understanding different models of addressing similar problems throughout research.

[Meeting information here](#)

Upcoming UKRN webinar - lay summaries

[Contributions to research by human and AI produced lay summaries](#)

19th October 2023 1:00 - 3:00 pm

Summaries of research for a lay, non-expert audience can improve the research process. Benefits may include helping other researchers understand a new topic; aid students or early career researchers in critically appraising and sharing their research; or communicating research with the wider public. In this webinar, experts will share their work on the creation of lay summaries and how they contribute to improving research. We will discuss the implications of both human and generative AI-produced summaries.

Speakers include:

Pen-Yuan Hsing, University of Bristol

Dr Anja Harrison, CEO, The Collaborative Library

Dr Avon Huxor, Associate Lecturer, Computer Science, University of Exeter

[Meeting information here](#)

Other upcoming events

[International data week 2023](#)

A Festival of Data, 23–26 October 2023, Salzburg, Austria

Programme: <https://internationaldataweek.org/idw2023/programme/>

Get involved

We'd love to hear from you. Let us share what you've been doing

email contact@ukrn.org

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